

Amplification Methods for the Microdetermination of Chloride Ion through Precipitation of Silver Iodide

S. A. RAHIM and A. AL-SALIHI*

Department of Chemistry, College of Science, University of Mosul, Iraq.

Manuscript received 3 May 1976; accepted 15 July 1976

Two simple gravimetric procedures for determination of small amounts of chloride are presented. Chloride ion in the range of 140-10 mg was estimated with high precision (standard deviation = 0.061 and 0.04 mg respectively), after single conversion of AgCl into AgI. For chloride concentrations of 10-0.05 mg a multi-amplification procedure was developed; the precision of 10 and 0.05 mg amounted to 0.023 and 0.005 mg, respectively. A simple apparatus was devised and used for this purpose. The AgI precipitate is advantageous than AgCl as the final weighing form since the former has smaller solubility, not much affected by photodecomposition, and has smaller gravimetric factor with corresponding increase in weight of precipitate.

ALTHOUGH gravimetric methods for the estimation of chloride ion have been reported, those methods are not sufficiently accurate when very small amounts are to be determined. The popularity of the gravimetric finish suggests that a micro gravimetric procedure with high precision seems desirable.

Precipitation of chloride ion as silver chloride suffers from the sensitivity of precipitate to direct sunlight or even to diffused sunlight¹. Furthermore, the solubility of AgCl in water is 1.8 mg/l at 25° and increases to 21.1 mg/l at 100°. However, silver iodide is far less liable to photodecomposition and has the solubility of 0.0035 mg/l of water at 20°. Using silver iodide as the weighing form would lower the value of the gravimetric factor from 0.2474 for Cl/AgCl to 0.1510 for Cl/AgI with the subsequent increase in weight of precipitate to nearly the double.

In this investigation, the first trials were to determine chloride by a single conversion of AgCl into AgI. The chloride ion is precipitated as AgCl which is filtered and washed; the precipitate dissolved in aqueous ammonia to produce the silver diamine complex plus the original chloride. The addition of sufficient iodide destroys the complex and precipitates the silver as silver iodide.

The crystalline silver iodide is insoluble in aqueous ammonia, easily filtered, washed, and dried; it has constant weight and stoichiometric composition along the range of 60°-700°.

Later on, the advantages of converting AgCl into AgI encouraged the idea that greater amplification, and hence higher sensitivity, would be possible by

applying the arithmetic progression reported previously². In the present work, we were able to determine as low as 0.05 mg of chloride ion with high accuracy. The washed precipitate of silver chloride is dissolved in aqueous ammonia; to the resulting solution (silver diamine complex and chloride) an excess of iodide ion is added to precipitate AgI. The latter removed by filtration and after washing, the filtrate containing the original amount of chloride is oxidized with nitrite to convert unreacted iodide into iodine removed by heating. The filtrate is then acidified, the chloride precipitated as AgCl and treated similarly to give silver iodide collected on the same filter as the original AgI. In this way, a second amount of AgI equivalent to the original AgCl is collected on the same filter. The process can be repeated as desired, then finally the accumulated AgI is weighed. The weight is divided by the number of amplification steps to obtain the weight of AgI equivalent to the original chloride.

Materials and Methods

Reagents: All the reagents used were of A. R. grade. Twice-distilled water was used all over the work.

Chloride solution. A stock solution of 0.1 M HCl was prepared and standardized gravimetrically. Another stock solution containing 1 mg of Cl⁻ per ml was prepared by dissolving 1.6479 g of sodium chloride, dried at 120°, in 1 liter of water and standardized gravimetrically. The latter solution was used with the multi-amplification procedure.

Dichlorofluorescein indicator 0.1% Na salt in water.

Nitric acid. Concentrated, 5%, 0.1%, and 0.03 M solutions were used.

Ammonia solution. 6 M solution was used.

*Department of Chemistry, College of Science, University of Baghdad, Iraq.

Potassium iodide solution. 0.5%.

Ammonium iodide solution. 0.7%.

Silver nitrate solution. 0.10 and 0.05 *M* solution were used.

Sodium nitrite. Solid.

Apparatus : The amplification apparatus is shown in Fig. 1.

Procedures

1. *Determination of Cl⁻ as AgI after a single conversion (10-140 mgCl⁻)* : Transfer an aliquot portion of the chloride solution into a 100-ml beaker. Dilute to about 50 ml with chlorine-free water. Add 1-2 drops of dichlorofluorescein indicator followed by 2-4 drops of concentrated nitric acid. Add 0.1 *M* silver nitrate solution, at a fast rate, keeping the solution well stirred during the addition until the AgCl precipitate turns pink. From the volume of AgNO₃ used, add more precipitant, with constant stirring, to provide a 10% excess. Cover the beaker and quickly heat the mixture near boiling for about 10 min with occasional stirring. The precipitate flocculates and the supernatant solution becomes almost clear. Place the beaker in the dark for 30 min. Transfer the precipitate to a sintered-glass crucible. Wash with 0.03 *M* HNO₃ till free of silver, then wash with little distilled water to remove nitric acid.

Treat the precipitate on the filter with the minimum amount of warm 6 *M* ammonia till complete dissolution. Dilute to 50 ml with water. Add, dropwise with constant stirring, 0.7% solution of ammonium iodide till complete precipitation of AgI. Add an excess of approximately 10% of the precipitant followed by a few milliliters of 5% nitric acid. Follow the same steps as for chloride, then collect the AgI precipitate on a sintered-glass crucible. Wash the precipitate with 0.03 *M* HNO₃ followed by a little water. Dry the precipitate at 120°-130° for an hour, then cool and weigh to constant weight. The weight of AgI multiplied by the gravimetric factor (0.1510) gives the weight of Cl⁻ in the sample.

2. *Micro-determination of Cl⁻ as AgI after multi-amplification (0.05-10 mgCl⁻)* : Cycle 1. Transfer an aliquot of the chloride solution into a small beaker. Add 1-2 drops of concentrated nitric acid followed by dropwise addition of an excess (ca. 10%) of silver nitrate solution, with constant stirring, for complete precipitation of AgCl. Heat the suspension, while stirring constantly, nearly to boiling until the precipitate coagulates and allow it to settle. Test for complete precipitation, then allow the precipitate and supernatant liquid to stand for 30 min. Filter off the precipitate on a sintered-glass crucible. Wash out the excessive Ag⁺ with 0.1% nitric acid solution and then with distilled water. Discard the filtrate.

Dissolve the precipitate on the filter in the minimum amount of ammonia solution. Precipitate the silver ions in the filtrate as AgI by adding the minimum amount of potassium iodide. Add 5% nitric acid solution (to prevent peptization) and heat nearly to boiling to

coagulate the AgI precipitate. Filter off the precipitate on the same glass filter. Set aside the precipitate after washing it well with 0.1% nitric acid solution and then with the minimum amount of water.

Cycle 2. Oxidize the filtrate, containing the original Cl⁻ and unreacted I⁻, by adding a few crystals of sodium nitrite and heat the solution nearly to boiling to remove iodine. Acidify the filtrate, treat it with an excess of AgNO₃ solution, and proceed as in cycle 1. Filter off the AgI precipitate on the same filter used in cycle 1. Thus two precipitates of AgI from both cycles are collected on the same filter.

Continue the amplification process till a weighable quantity of precipitate is obtained. The procedure is carried out by using a simple amplification apparatus (Fig. 1). Finally, wash the collected precipitate, dry, and weigh it. Divide the weight by the number of cycles to obtain the original amount of silver iodide.

Fig. 1. Gravimetric Amplification Apparatus

Results and Discussion

Table I shows that the AgCl/AgI amplification method could be applied to the determination of Cl⁻ in amounts of small as 0.7 mg with great accuracy. Chloride ion in the range of 10-0.05 mg could be determined with almost 100% recovery by using the

necessary number of cycles (Table 2). Chloride ions less than 0.05 mg could not be reliably precipitated; the solubility of AgCl is ca. 10^{-5} which corresponds to ca. 0.01 mg/10 ml.

the $Ag_2S/AgCl$ amplification method reported previously². Further simplicity and rapidity is attained through weighing of the collected AgI precipitate directly instead of dissolving the accumulated Ag_2S followed by reprecipitation and weighing as $AgCl^2$.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Cl^- AS AgI.

Chloride content (mg)	Chloride found (mg)		
	141.82	141.83,	141.69,
70.91	71.00,	69.82,	70.76
35.45	35.39,	35.55,	34.97
14.18	14.09,	14.15,	14.08
10.20	10.11,	10.08,	10.13
7.09	7.14,	7.08,	6.98

TABLE—2. COMPARISON OF $AgCl/S^{2-}$ AND $AgCl/I^-$ AMPLIFICATION REACTIONS FOR THE MICRODETERMINATION OF Cl^- ION.

Chloride present (mg)	Chloride found* (mg)		no. of cycles
	$AgCl/S^{2-}$ method ^a	$AgCl/I^-$ method	
10.00	10.01	10.01	1
5.00	5.00	5.00	1
1.00	1.01	1.01	1
0.50	0.50	0.50	1
0.10	0.09	0.10	3
0.05	0.05	0.05	5

*Mean of 3 determinations.

Five cycles are necessary for determination of 0.05 mg of Cl^- compared with 8 cycles in case of using

Obviously, the present method can only be successful as long as the initial stage of precipitation is quantitative each time it is used. It is important therefore to ensure that care is taken to allow sufficient time for complete precipitation of AgCl, each time $AgNO_3$ is added. After dissolving the AgCl precipitate and precipitating Ag^+ as AgI, the excessive iodide is oxidized with sodium nitrite into iodine with no effect on the Cl^- released in solution (the standard oxidation potential of NO/HNO_2 is lower than that of Cl^-/Cl_2). Errors are expected to cancel each other in an arithmetic amplification procedure such as this. The precision of the method 1 was tested by replicate (5) determinations of 140 and 10 mg of chloride by application of the recommended procedure 1. This yielded standard deviations of 0.061 and 0.04 mg respectively. The standard deviations of the amplification procedure 2 for 10, 1 and 0.05 mg of chloride were also determined and found to be 0.023 mg (5 analyses of 1 cycle), 0.05 mg (5 analyses of 3 cycles), and 0.005 mg (6 analyses of 5 cycles), respectively.

References

1. G. E. FLENDELL and J. I. HOFFMAN, *Bur. Stand. J. Res.*, 1930, 4, 109.
2. S. A. RAHIM, H. ABDULAHED and T.S. WEST, *Microchim. Acta* (Wien), 1974, 111.

Fig. 1. Gravimetric Amplification Apparatus.